

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH DIGITAL TOOLS

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Abstract

Speaking is the one type of productive skills but in order to communicate in a target language listening (a receptive skill) is also increasingly important when having a conversation. There are many factors to consider with teaching speaking. This essay will examine three main factors: cultural, learning and L1 factors. It is important to understand that many cognitive processes are taking place when a student speaks in the target language and so fluency can be a key focus when improving the skill.

Key words:

English language learner, specific circumstance, unstructured discipline, vocabulary, different reasons, advancement, effectiveness, various levels, aspect

Аннотация

Разговорный речь — это один из видов продуктивных навыков, но для общения на целевом языке аудирование (рецептивный навык) также становится все более важным во время разговора. Есть много факторов, которые следует учитывать при обучении разговорной речи. На этой статье будут рассмотрены три основных фактора: культурный, учебный и L1. Важно понимать, что многие когнитивные процессы происходят, когда учащийся говорит на целевом языке, поэтому беглость речи может быть ключевым моментом при совершенствовании навыка.

Ключевые слова:

Изучающий английский язык, аспект, конкретное обстоятельство, неструктурированная дисциплина, словарный запас, разные причины, продвижение, эффективность, различные уровни

Izoh

Nutq - samarali ko'nikmalarning bir turi, ammo maqsadli tilda muloqot qilish uchun tinglash (reseptiv qobiliyat) suhbat paytida ham tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Nutqni o'rgatishda ko'plab omillarni hisobga olish kerak. Ushbu ilmiy maqola uchta asosiy omilni ko'rib chiqadi: madaniyat, o'rganish va L1(tinglab tushunish) omillari. Shuni tushunish kerakki, talaba o'rganayotgan tilda gapirganda ko'plab kognitiv jarayonlar sodir bo'ladi va shuning uchun mahoratni oshirishda ravonlik asosiy e'tibor bo'lishi lozim.

Kalit so'zlar:

Ingliz tilini o'rganuvchi, muayyan sharoit, so'z boyligi, turli sabablar, rivojlanish, samaradorlik, turli darajalar, tartib intizomning mavjudsizligi, nuqtai nazar, ravonlik

The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on modern methods of teaching English has been limited. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it. ESP is a field, that English language learner students need to consider when learning English for agriculture, economy, financial aspects, software engineering, pharmaceutical, medical, governmental issues and different orders. It doesn't contemplate general English however reaches out to extraordinary vocabulary utilize where understudies may confront numerous issues when learning. In reality, ESP is an unstructured discipline as Hutchinson and Waters (1987) note. It has not been developed hence but rather because of various different reasons: the requests of Brave New World, an upheaval in etymology, and the emphasis on the student. This opened doors to numerous individuals to learn English since it turned into the language of innovation and trade, particularly after the advancements came about because of Oil emergencies of the mid 1970s.

Another reason is variety; phonetics is viewed as a depiction of English tenets use (sentence structure portrayal) yet this view has been moved to portrayal of dialect use as indicated by the specific circumstance. Actually, language learning has been situated towards need and effectiveness for various ESP students. ESP has risen in the sixteenth century where the generation of particular vocabularies and expression books for ambassadors, specialists and others has occurred.

Teaching speaking in ESP classrooms is defined by this way. To be able to define ESP, it is necessary to clarify its position towards the rest of ELT ("English Language Teaching"). Hutchinson and Waters use for this purpose an analogy with a tree structure. It can be concluded that there are various levels of ESP courses. At the top, individual courses can be seen, the lower level than shows that each ESP class can be further categorized as an EAP class ("English for Academic Purposes") or an EOP class ("English for Occupational Purposes"). Furthermore, each individual ESP course is a part of one of the broader ESP courses – EST ("English for Science and Technology"), EBE ("English for Business and Economics") or ESS ("English for Social Sciences") (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987). Nevertheless, based on the tree structure, it is apparent that every English course has the same roots and belongs into the general category of language teaching which suggests that there might be some common background for learning and teaching in all the classes. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) attempt to define ESP negatively by saying: a) ESP is not a matter of teaching "specialized varieties" of English; b) ESP is not just a matter of Science words and grammar for Scientists, Hotel words and grammar for Hotel staff and so on; c) ESP is not different in kind from any other form of language teaching, in that it should be based in the first instance in principles of effective and efficient learning.

This stands against the general belief that ESP courses are predominantly based on acquisition of vocabulary related to the field of study. According to the above-mentioned definition, it might seem that there is no clear distinction between ESP and other types of language teaching, thus a question of what makes teaching and learning ESP different arises. The answer is provided by Hutchinson and Waters (1987) who claim that, "ESP must be seen as an approach not as a product". They continue to explain that the ESP is "Based on the

learner need” and can be defined as “An approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to contents and method are based on the learners’ reason for learning” (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987. Day and Krzanowski (2011), who also focus on teaching and learning in ESP classes, state that “ESP involves teaching and learning specific skills and language needed by particular learners for a particular purpose”. Based on the definitions, it can be said that each ESP class is different, learners have various needs and reasons for studying, they pursue specific goals and these factors put high demands on the teachers, whose main task is to identify those needs and design a suitable course.

To conclude it should be noted that, the teacher of 21 century Speaking and teaching speaking is the main goal of language. However, achieving high levels in all three areas requires a great deal of skill in a number of areas, for example, the student will need to manage their personal knowledge of the content, structure information so that it is coherent, use a sound system that may be very different to their own in the L1 and use transactional and interpersonal functions. Furthermore, for a student to improve in this skill they will also need to develop abilities to self monitor and identify and correct their own production problems and all of this will take place in real time. Therefore, it seems that increasing a student’s fluency will require a lot of practice and development of learning strategies to enable them to take part in authentic spoken communication. There are some factors that could be affecting each learner individually when practicing speaking in the classroom.

should have traditional concepts and techniques of classroom teaching and should adopt the recent and innovative teaching techniques. English communication skill teachers must be innovative, creative and resourceful with thorough knowledge of the subject and adopt new techniques to change social economic status of our country. Whatever may be the methods and approaches, the most pragmatic and the desirable thing seems to explore the possibility of using the under used and valuable materials which will definitely facilitate the learning and teaching of language skills. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of multimedia technology and the spawning of a technologically-savvy generation of youths¹.

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